

Origins of Contaminated Air

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ABSTRACT

The issue and debate around the contamination of the breathing air supply in aircraft has existed since the dawn of pressurized flight. Since the introduction of 'bleed air' in the late 1940s, aviation has seen a steady increase in reports of the air supply being contaminated. From US Air Force crews in the 1950s being adversely affected in flight, to passenger and crew exposures still occurring in 2017. This paper seeks to provide the reader with a brief overview of the history of this important on-going health and flight safety issue.

INTRODUCTION

Aviation as we know it was born in 1903 when the Wright brothers carried out their short but historic flight. Six years later in 1909, Louis Beiror became the first man to fly the English Channel. In 1909 Alcock and Brown carried out the first crossing of the Atlantic having flown 1,890 miles (3,040 km) in 15 hours 57 minutes. This was followed in 1927 when Charles Lindbergh made the first solo nonstop flight across the Atlantic from Roosevelt Field, Long Island, New York, to Paris, France. Lindbergh covered the 33 1/2-hour, 3,600 statute miles (5,800 km) in a single-engine purpose-built Ryan monoplane, Spirit of St. Louis. In 1939, the first jet-powered aircraft flew, the Heinkel He 178 and on 14th October 1947, Chuck Yeager broke the sound barrier in a Bell X1.

In just 44 years humankind had gone from a few hundred feet to faster than the speed of sound and beyond the

troposphere and into the stratosphere.

Lindbergh and other record breakers knew high altitude flight was needed for long sector flying to avoid the potentially serious consequences of adverse weather located in the troposphere. At altitudes above 10,000 feet (3,000 m) above sea level, there is a need to protect crew and passengers from the risk of a number of physiological problems caused by the low outside air pressure above that altitude. Pressurization could solve the problem of not having to supply supplemental oxygen to prevent hypoxia.

The troposphere is the lowest layer of Earth's atmosphere, and is also where nearly all weather conditions take place. It contains approximately 75% of the atmosphere's mass and 99% of the total mass of water vapor and aerosols. The average depths of the troposphere are 65,617 ft (20,000 m) in the tropics, 55,774 ft (17,000 m) in the mid latitudes, and 22,966 ft (7,000 m) in the polar regions in winter. The temperature of the troposphere generally decreases as altitude increases by about 2°C per 1,000 ft. The pressure of the atmosphere is maximum at sea level and decreases with altitude.

The experiences of the pioneer high altitude balloon and fixed wing pilots showed aviation that to survive high altitude flight, a pressurized cabin would be needed. The first aircraft to fly with a pressurized cockpit was the Engineering Division USD-9A that first flew in 1921. The first pressurized passenger airliner was Boeing Model 307 Stratoliner that flew in 1938. Cabin superchargers ensured the aircraft could be pressurized by providing enough air to ensure it had an 8,000 foot cabin whilst flying at 15,000 feet. AiResearch Cabin Blowers led the way and providing enough air to pressurize leading aircraft of the time such as the Boeing B-29, which first flew in 1942, and the Lockheed L-647/749 Constellation, which first flew in 1943.

The introduction of jet engines in the 1940s provided a new potential way to pressurize aircraft. The Lockheed F-80 Shooting Star that first flew in 1944 took air

from the engine blower section of the General Electric J33-A-23 Single-stage centrifugal flow engine to pressurize the cockpit. At 30,000 feet the cabin altitude was 18,000 feet.

In the early 1950s the J57 engine took jet engine design to new levels and air was bled off the compression section of the axial flow engine. These new engines operated at far higher internal temperatures and needed a new type of oil to replace the previously used mineral oil. These new oils developed under military specification MIL-L-7808 were man made synthetic oils known as Type One or Three centistoke oils.

P. R. Bassett in his 1935 paper 'Passenger Comfort in Air Transportation' had stated that "even a trace of smell causes extreme discomfort in the air". Patent specification 651.576 entitled 'Improvements in and relating to Aircraft with Pressurised Cabins' proposed that an air 'Purifier' be fitted between the engine air off take and the aircraft cabin but 70 years on the only aircraft flying with any form of bleed air filtration are DHL Boeing 757 aircraft that have cockpit filter units fitted to their Boeing 757 Rolls-Royce powered aircraft.

Although aircraft like the Boeing 377 Stratocruiser had carbon monoxide detectors and basic filters fitted, none of the early jet aircraft had any form of contaminated air warning systems fitted, which is still the case over 60 years later in civil passenger jet aircraft.

The introduction of these new oils in the J57 and other new modern jet engines led very quickly to a large number of reported contaminated air events on aircraft. Boeing in their document D-14766-2 from 1953 state in relation to oil contamination issues on their B-52 aircraft that "*The possible toxic effect of contamination is still unknown' and that 'Obvious increases in the level of contamination level were noted during changes in engine power conditions.'*"¹

Douglas in their 1954 XC-132 Engine Compressor Bleed Air Contamination Study relating to J-57 and T-57 engine contamination problems state: "*Apparently the*

occurrence is completely erratic, with no predictable pattern since contamination has occurred all modes of airplane operation, such as take-off, high altitude cruise, descent and taxi. So far there is no known condition or sequence of conditions, which will reliably reproduce the trouble."²

One of the first pilot reports of contaminated air was made on 15 May 1954 by William J. van Every.³ He stated: "*At approximately 1530 hours on 15 May 1954, I was flying aircraft number 52-1436, an RB-57A, in a three (3) plane formation from Shaw Air Force Base, South Carolina. Approximately 40 minutes after take-off while flying over an overcast at 7000 feet, I experienced blurred vision, became nauseated and experienced considerable dizziness. I recall no strange or unpleasant odors, nor did I taste anything out of the ordinary. I did feel a definite dryness of mouth and throat. This condition lasted possibly a minute or two. As I became more aware of the situation or nearly to the passing out point I recall dropping back from the formation and opening the clear vision window and unhooking the oxygen mask. Fresh air from this open window seemed to relieve the unpleasant conditions I felt.*"

Captain William Hardin made a similar report two days later: "*At approximately 1015 hours on 16 May 1954 I became sick while flying RB-57A aircraft 852-1444. I was flying at 10,000 feet occasionally climbing over clouds up to 12,000 feet, aircraft had no oxygen aboard. I was flying with pressurization on, dump valve closed and full cold position due to heat. After being airborne approximately 45 minutes I became sick (metallic taste) to stomach with dryness of mouth, throat and stomach. Pressurization was turned off and clear vision panel opened and I immediately began feeling better. Flight was continued for about 1 hour and 15 minutes with no further effects during flight or after flight.*"³

A 1955 paper by Ted A. Loomis, Captain, MC and Stephen Krop, Ph. D. entitled 'Cabin Air Contamination in RB-57A' states:³

- The present studies involving exposure of humans

to the cabin air at the engine test facility while the lubricant was sprayed into the intake of the engine demonstrated that illness can occur as a result of such exposure.

- Smoke or fog is not an adequate indication that excessive lubricant is being used by the engine as symptoms appeared before amounts of the lubricant great enough to produce smoke were present.
- It would be reasonable to expect similar illness following prolonged exposure to even lower concentrations of the lubricant (and/or its breakdown products) than were used in this study.

The aviation industry was concerned enough by the possibility of contaminated air that many early passenger jet aircraft used turbo compressors rather than bleed air to ensure the air could not become contaminated. These included aircraft such as the Boeing Dash 80 (Boeing 707), Douglas DC-8, Convair 880 and 990. The use of turbo compressors was suggested in a 1955 North American Aviation paper entitled 'Elimination of Engine Bleed Air Contamination'.⁴ The paper stated they had been aware of the oil contamination issue for the last two years, they suspected compressor bearing seals were the main source, they had taken an in-depth look at possible filters and concluded that: *'The Separate Compressor As A Solution – This method of eliminating contamination is considered to be the most positive... also the heaviest, most complicated and most expensive.'*

Despite well documented evidence of contaminated air events occurring, other European aircraft manufacturers using British Rolls-Royce engines opted to introduce unfiltered bleed air into the aircraft cabin for pressurization yet installed no form of contaminated air detection systems to warn when the air was contaminated. Aircraft such as the later versions of the Comet and the Sud Aviation SE 210 Caravelle. The last aircraft before the introduction of the Boeing 787 to fly without using bleed air was the Vickers VC-10, which flew in 1962. The Boeing 787, which first flew in

December 2009, was the first airliner to return to not using bleed air after 47 years of continuous bleed air use in aircraft. The Boeing 787 opted to use electrical compressors and to have a totally bleed free architecture.

Since 1962 when all aircraft have used bleed air there have been a growing number of reported contaminated air issues. A 1973 paper by Aviation Medicine and Safety Research entitled 'Analytical Considerations Concerned with Cephalalgia on the DC-10' states: *"it appeared to be quite probable that the source of the headaches could be contaminants derived from the engine bleed air source for cabin pressurization."*⁵ A 1984 BAe 146 Service Information Leaflet SIL 21-7 states: "If the system becomes contaminated by oil, unpleasant cabin odour may be alleviated by..." and goes on to make suggestions of how to manage the problem.⁶ In 1984 a US occupational health physician prepared a report for a flight attendant union suggesting *"Mobil Jet II has been implicated as a causative agent"* with adverse health effects in those exposed.⁷ It was reported in 1991 that captains in East West airlines were "making a PA announcement to passengers and apologizing for the 'sweaty socks' smell" linked to oil contamination of the air supply.⁸

The U.S. ban on in-flight smoking began with domestic flights of two hours or less in April 1988 and was extended to domestic flights of six hours or less in February 1990, and then to all domestic and international flights in 2000. The smoking ban led to a significant increase in reporting of contaminated air events after the smoking ban, as they could no longer be masked by smoking smells.

In 1999, the term 'aerotoxic syndrome' was suggested to explain the health effects being seen in crew and passengers from those exposed to contaminated air in aircraft.

A Sunday Times headline of 17th September 2017 stated that: 'EasyJet to filter toxic air in cabins' as a consequence of easyJet becoming the first airline in the world to order the new Pall Aerospace 'Total cabin air

filtration' system being developed by Pall Aerospace. The system is accompanied by a new sensor system to warn when the air is contaminated by engine oils, hydraulic fluids, or carbon monoxide.

There are over 20,000 commercial airliners flying today around the globe using a bleed air system to provide breathing air to occupants yet 99.9% have any form of bleed air filtration or contaminated air warning systems fitted.

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